

Ultrasonic Coagulation of Selenium Sol in Absence of Oxygen and in Presence of Organic Substances

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On ultrasonation of unprotected hydrosol of selenium, prepared by reducing selenium dioxide with hydrazine hydrate, becomes so unstable that it coagulates after 4-5 hours of exposure in presence of oxygen, but in its absence sol shows marked stability in ultrasonic field and does not coagulate. The significant role of oxygen in relation to ultrasonic coagulation of selenium sol is ascribed to removal of stabilising selenite ions from the double layer and to the production of selenic acid, which explains the increase in hydrogen-ion concentration and specific conductance as well. The inhibition of ultrasonic coagulation of selenium sol in presence of glycol, dioxane, and urea has been attributed to their high vapour pressure and low dielectric constant, surface tension, and internal pressure values.

The dispersing and coagulating influences of high frequency, inaudible sound waves have been studied by many workers. From this laboratory Prakash and co-workers¹ published their results on a number of sols exposed to ultrasonic waves. In an earlier communication², the present authors reported their results on the influence of ultrasonic waves on manganese dioxide sol in absence of oxygen. The results on coagulation of selenium sol, when subjected to ultrasonic waves in absence of oxygen and in presence of ethylene glycol, dioxane, urea, and glucose, have been reported here.

EXPERIMENTAL

The selenium sol was prepared by reduction of selenium dioxide by hydrazine hydrate, as modified by Kruyt and Van Arkel³. 1.5*M* Hydrazine hydrate (5 ml) was added to water (90 ml) and the solution heated to 100°. 0.1*M* Selenium dioxide solution (4 ml) was then added to the hot solution. After the mixture had become dark yellow, more selenium dioxide solution (1 ml) was added; heating was then stopped and the mixture left for 10 min. It was then diluted to 400 ml with distilled water. The sol was further purified by dialysis in a cellophane bag.

A constant volume (30 ml) of the sol was taken in a Jena glass bottle and exposed to ultrasonic waves having barium titanate as a transducer with a frequency of 1 Mc/s and power 225 watt/cm². The sol was studied at three dilutions, viz., A, A/2, and A/3, where A is the concentration of the original sol. The changes in hydrogen-ion concentration and specific conductance were noted after each exposure. The same experiments were

1. *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1959, **36**, 396; this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 399, 696; *Kolloid Z.*, 1961, **175**, 56.
2. Prakash and Prakash, *Kolloid Z.*, 1963, **188**, 136.
3. *Kolloid Z.*, 1923, **32**, 29.

repeated in absence of oxygen, *i.e.* in nitrogen atmosphere (Tables I—IV) The air of the bottle containing the sol was replaced by bubbling oxygen-free nitrogen through it for half an hour.

To study the effect of ultrasonic radiations on this sol in presence of glycol, dioxane, urea, and glucose, different amounts of these non-electrolytes were added to the sol, keeping the total volume constant, and then the mixtures were exposed to the ultrasonic field (Tables V—VIII). The results were compared with those having no non-electrolyte.

TABLE I

Sol A.

Conc. of the sol = 0.21 g./litre. R. F. output voltage = 1.8 KV (approx.).

Temp. = $27^{\circ} \pm 0.2^{\circ}$.

Time of exposure.	In presence of air.		In absence of oxygen.	
	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.
0 min.	0.286 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	6.90 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	0.286	6.90
30	0.621	6.55	0.302	6.90
60	0.824	6.15	0.385	6.80
90	1.215	5.80	0.479	6.70
120	1.768	5.50	0.504	6.65
150	2.292	5.10	0.596	6.50
180	2.839	4.80	0.688	6.35
240	Coagulated	..	0.845	6.10

No coagulation

TABLE II

Sol A/2.

Time of exposure.	In presence of air.		In absence of oxygen.	
	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.
0 min.	0.237 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.05	0.237 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.05
30	0.489	6.60	0.249	6.95
60	0.709	6.15	0.265	6.80
90	0.975	5.70	0.346	6.70
120	1.175	5.40	0.398	6.55
150	1.453	4.90	0.447	6.40
180	1.829	4.55	0.515	6.30
210	2.229	3.95	0.581	6.20
270	Coagulated	..	0.769	5.85

No coagulation

TABLE III

Sol A/3.

Time of exposure.	In presence of air.		In absence of oxygen.	
	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.
0 min.	0.131 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.10	0.131 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.10
30	0.353	6.60	0.151	7.00
60	0.618	6.00	0.164	6.90
90	0.833	5.60	0.205	6.70
120	1.080	5.10	0.261	6.60
150	1.347	4.60	0.333	6.60
180	1.568	4.20	0.389	6.50
210	1.894	3.85	0.463	6.40
240	2.106	3.70	0.505	6.20
270	2.221	3.70	0.669	6.05
330	Coagulated	..	0.896	5.80

No coagulation

TABLE IV

Visual change in colour in sol A.

Time of exposure.	In presence of air.	In absence of oxygen.
0 min.	Orange-yellow with turbidity	Orange-yellow with turbidity
30	Do	Do
60	Orange, less turbidity	Do
90	Do	Do
120	Dark red	Orange, with less turbidity
180	Do	Do
240	Coagulated	Faint red

TABLE V

With ethylene glycol.

Conc. the sol = 0.0615g./litre.

Time of exposure.	Sol only.		Sol (20ml) + ethylene glycol (10 ml).		Sol (15 ml) + ethylene glycol (15 ml).	
	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.
0 min.	0.254 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.20	0.143 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.10	0.081 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.35
30	0.422	6.95	0.191	7.00	0.090	7.15
60	0.594	6.60	0.249	6.90	0.110	7.00
90	0.791	6.30	0.288	6.75	0.129	6.80
120	0.914	5.90	0.348	6.50	0.241	6.55
180	1.313	5.00	0.448	6.30	0.341	6.30
240	1.833	3.90	0.580	6.00	0.437	6.10

Partial coagulation No coagulation No coagulation

TABLE VI

With dioxane.

Conc. of the sol = 0.0615g./litre.

Time of exposure.	Sol only.		Sol (20 ml)+dioxane (10ml).		Sol (15 ml)+dioxane (15 ml).	
	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.
0 min	0.254 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.20	0.322 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	6.90	0.187 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.30
30	0.391	6.80	0.362	6.75	0.239	7.20
60	0.603	6.20	0.413	6.65	0.269	7.10
90	0.808	5.75	0.454	6.50	0.298	6.95
120	1.003	5.20	0.485	6.40	0.321	6.80
180	1.389	4.50	0.586	6.15	0.397	6.60
240	1.959	3.85	0.693	5.00	0.449	6.35

TABLE VII

With glucose.

Conc. of the sol = 0.0532 g./litre.

Time of exposure.	Sol (20 ml) only.		50% Glucose soln. + sol (20 ml).		10% Glucose soln. + sol (20 ml).	
	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.
0 min.	0.232 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.30	0.236 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.20	0.258 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.1
60	0.342	6.60	0.308	6.20	0.326	6.2
120	0.499	5.60	0.519	5.10	0.540	4.9
180	0.607	4.70	0.736	4.20	0.945	4.1
240	0.876	4.05	1.319	3.65	2.010	3.5

TABLE VIII

With urea.

Conc. of the sol = 0.0532 g./litre.

Time of exposure.	Sol (20 ml) only.		5% Urea soln. + sol (20 ml).		10% Urea soln. + sol (20 ml).	
	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.	Sp. cond. $\times 10^4$.	pH.
0 min.	0.234 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.40	0.354 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.40	0.433 ohm ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	7.40
60	0.302	6.50	0.390	7.20	0.462	7.30
120	0.519	5.70	0.417	7.05	0.497	7.20
180	0.642	4.90	0.449	6.90	0.513	7.15
240	0.916	3.65	0.475	6.75	0.532	7.10

DISCUSSION

From Tables I-III, it is clear that ultrasonic waves are less effective to hydrosol of selenium in absence of oxygen than in its presence. In the latter case, the sol coagulates within 4-5 hours of exposure, but in absence of oxygen no coagulation takes place. Of course, the stability of the sol in the latter case also goes on decreasing gradually.

The specific conductance of sol A has been found to increase on exposure to ultrasonic waves in presence of oxygen from 0.286 to 2.839×10^{-4} ($\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), but in absence of oxygen the increase is from 0.286 to 0.688×10^{-4} ($\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) only during 180 minutes of exposure. Similar observations were found with diluted sols.

pH of the sol also decreases with the time of exposure. pH values change from 6.9 to 4.8 in presence of oxygen, but in its absence the decrease is from 6.9 to 6.1 only. It shows that the acidity developed in the medium in absence of oxygen is very little.

In sol A the visual change in colour (Table IV) as a result of its exposure to the ultrasonic waves is from orange-yellow to dark red, whereas in absence of oxygen, the change in colour is not much pronounced. Only the turbidity disappears and the sol finally becomes faint red. This change in colour shows that the colloidal particles are increasing in size.

The most stable unprotected sol of selenium is formed in presence of a small excess of selenous acid or its salts. The sol is therefore negatively charged because of the strong adsorption of the selenite ions which become the inner part of the double layer surrounding the particles.

It appears that under the action of ultrasonic waves, the stabilising selenite ions become free and form selenous acid. This acid on oxidation with activated oxygen⁴ forms selenic acid. Selenic acid, being stronger acid, on dissociation yields hydrogen ions which are preferentially adsorbed in the double layer with the result that the negative charges on the colloidal particles are neutralised by positive hydrogen ions, and the sol coagulates.

The selenic acid, so formed, goes to increase the hydrogen-ion concentration and specific conductance of the sol. In absence of oxygen, the occurrence of the above reaction leading to the formation of selenic acid is not possible. Therefore the sol will be less affected. In this case only, the mechanical action is predominant and the slight increase in hydrogen-ion concentration and specific conductance may be due to the fact that as the electrical double layer is distorted, the selenite ions adsorbed in the double layer become gradually free and form selenous acid with water in the medium, whereas in the presence of oxygen, the charge neutralisation as a result of the formation of selenic acid as well as the removal of stabilising selenite ions due to distortion of the double layer facilitates the process of coalescence, and hence the coagulation.

Tables V-VIII show that the influence of ultrasonic waves on the sol is very little in presence of glycol, dioxane, and urea and slightly greater in presence of glucose. It shows that the sol is stabilised in presence of glycol, dioxane, and urea and sensitised in presence of glucose. Sensitising effect of glucose is surprising and contrary to the expectation. The inhibiting effect of glycol, dioxane, and urea may be explained as follows.

4. Weissler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 1077.

Inhibition by these organic substances may be due to their high vapour pressure values which cause the suppression of cavitation. Virtanen and Ellfolk⁵ and Bresler⁶ have reported that by addition of substances of higher vapour pressure, such as ether, ammonia, and acetone, the breakdown of cavitation bubble is prevented.

Increase in the amount of the organic substances results in the decrease of the dielectric constant of the medium. Water and hydrogen peroxide, having maximum dielectric constant value, facilitate the ultrasonic activity. It appears therefore that increase in the dielectric constant favours cavitation and hence greater activity of ultrasonic waves.

Internal pressure⁷ of water is five to six times greater than that of most of the organic liquids. It may be expected that substances of low internal pressure would inhibit the cavitation effect.

Inhibition by organic substances may also be attributed to their low surface tension value. Heuter and Bolt⁸ have suggested that higher the surface tension of the reaction solution, the greater will be the amount of energy released upon collapse of the cavitation bubble. Thus greater the surface tension of the medium, the faster should be the rate of ultrasonic action. Since organic substances have lower surface tension values (surface tension of water 2-3 times that of organic liquids), hence in their presence ultrasonic effect would be less.

The authors are grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for awarding a grant for this work and also for awarding a fellowship to one of them (Om Prakash).

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Received May 15, 1964.

5. *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, **6**, 660.

6. *Physicochim.*, *URSS*, 1940, **12**, 323.

7. Srivastava and Berkowitz, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1963, **41**, 1787.

8. 'Sonics', John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1955, p. 240.